

A PROOF OF HÖLDER'S INEQUALITY BY ALGEBRAIC SYMMETRY

Cauchy's forward-backward induction [1, 3] or some variants of it such as [2] can be used to prove some elementary inequalities including the AGM and Hölder's inequalities. Another variation exploiting algebraic symmetry is presented for the AGM inequality, then extended to Hölder's inequality for rational exponents; in particular, a direct $n \rightarrow n + 1$ induction is realized in an algebraically straightforward way, without relying on such a traditional instrument as backward induction or a density argument.

Proposition 1. *For a positive integer n and any positive real numbers a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n ,*

$$(1) \quad \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n a_k}{n} \geq \sqrt[n]{\prod_{k=1}^n a_k}.$$

Proof. For an integer $n > 1$, let $\mu = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n a_k}{n}$ and $\alpha = a_{n+1} > 0$.

Denote the symmetric means by:

$$M = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n+1} a_k}{n+1} = \frac{n\mu + \alpha}{n+1} \quad \text{and} \quad W = \frac{n\alpha + \mu}{n+1}.$$

Assume (1) holds for any arbitrary choice of a_k 's. Then we have the symmetric identities:

$$(2a) \quad M = \frac{(n-1)\mu + W}{n} \geq \sqrt[n]{\mu^{n-1}W}$$

$$(2b) \quad W = \frac{(n-1)\alpha + M}{n} \geq \sqrt[n]{\alpha^{n-1}M}$$

Solving this system (2) for M and applying (1) yields:

$$\begin{aligned} M^{n+1} &\geq \mu^n \alpha \geq \left(\prod_{k=1}^n a_k \right) \alpha = \prod_{k=1}^{n+1} a_k \\ \implies M &\geq \sqrt[n+1]{\prod_{k=1}^{n+1} a_k}, \text{ i.e., } \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n+1} a_k}{n+1} \geq \sqrt[n+1]{\prod_{k=1}^{n+1} a_k}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 2. Jensen's and Minkowski's inequalities can be proven likewise.

Lemma 3. *For any positive integers m and n and any (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) in \mathbb{R}^n ,*

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k| \right)^{\frac{m-1}{m}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |y_k| \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \geq \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^{\frac{m-1}{m}} |y_k|^{\frac{1}{m}}.$$

Proof. Lemma 3 is true for $m = 2$ by Cauchy-Schwarz inequality. Assume neither vector in Lemma 3 is null, which is a trivial case.

Denote the symmetric terms by:

$$\begin{aligned} X &= \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|, & Y &= \sum_{k=1}^n |y_k|, \\ M &= X^{\frac{m}{m+1}} Y^{\frac{1}{m+1}}, & W &= X^{\frac{1}{m+1}} Y^{\frac{m}{m+1}}, \\ N &= \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^{\frac{m}{m+1}} |y_k|^{\frac{1}{m+1}}, & Z &= \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^{\frac{1}{m+1}} |y_k|^{\frac{m}{m+1}}. \end{aligned}$$

By such algebraic manipulation as in (2), the symmetric identities follow:

$$(3) \quad M = X^{\frac{m-1}{m}} W^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad \text{and} \quad W = Y^{\frac{m-1}{m}} M^{\frac{1}{m}}.$$

Solving this system (3) for M , we get:

$$(4) \quad M^{\frac{m^2-1}{m^2}} = X^{\frac{m-1}{m}} Y^{\frac{m-1}{m^2}}.$$

We multiply both sides of (4) by $N^{\frac{1}{m^2}}$ and apply the induction hypothesis twice to symmetric expressions to get:

$$N^{\frac{1}{m^2}} M^{\frac{m^2-1}{m^2}} = X^{\frac{m-1}{m}} \left(Y^{\frac{m-1}{m}} N^{\frac{1}{m}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \geq X^{\frac{m-1}{m}} Z^{\frac{1}{m}} \geq N,$$

or $M \geq N$. □

Corollary 4. *Applying Lemma 3 in place of Cauchy's dyadic forward-backward induction [3], we get Hölder's inequality for any rational weights:*

$$\prod_{j=1}^m \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k^{(j)}| \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \geq \sum_{k=1}^n \prod_{j=1}^m |x_k^{(j)}|^{\frac{1}{m}} \implies \prod_{i=1}^l \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k^{(i)}| \right)^{w_i} \geq \sum_{k=1}^n \prod_{i=1}^l |x_k^{(i)}|^{w_i},$$

where l , m and n are positive integers and w_i 's are arbitrary positive rational weights whose sum equals 1.

REFERENCES

1. Augustin-Louis Cauchy, *Cours d'analyse de l'École royale polytechnique; 1.re partie. analyse algébrique*, pp. 457–459, de l'Imprimerie royale, Paris, 1821.
2. Kong-Ming Chong, *The arithmetic mean—geometric mean inequality: A new proof*, Math. Mag. **49** (1976), 87–88.
3. G. H. Hardy, J. E. Littlewood, and George Pólya, *Inequalities*, pp. 22–23, Cambridge: University Press, 1934.